

Deliverables 2.1, 2.2, 2.3 of the Working-package 2 of the project
ENAMARE¹

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This document contains three interrelated deliverables:

- D2.1 (month 8) Working document with terminology, framework and tools acquired through training with DST framework.
- D2.2. (month 18) A glossary defining and characterising specific fit concepts from DST to address aesthetics from an interdisciplinary enactive perspective.
- D2.3 (month 22) Elaborate a specific glossary defining and characterizing general concepts from DST to address cognitive processes.

For the sake of clarity, the structure of the document is as follows: (1) an introduction of the general framework of dynamic systems theory; (2) a glossary with terms of dynamics systems theory relevant for research on different aspects of cognition; (3) a glossary with the definition of terms directly related to ENAMARE; (4) a general bibliography of research papers and theoretical publications of dynamic systems theory.

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1. Introduction: dynamic systems theory

According to Evan Thompson (2010, 38), the central tenet of dynamical approach to cognition is that “natural cognition –cognition in evolved, living agents– is a dynamic phenomenon and accordingly needs to be understood from the perspective of the science of dynamic systems”. Thus, the first essential concept is that of *dynamic system*. A dynamic system is any system that changes over time. Accordingly, *dynamical systems theory* is the mathematical apparatus used to describe the way a dynamic system evolves over time. The evolution of a dynamical system is described as changes in *state*. An state of a system is given as the result of the different state variable of a system. The totality of all states of a system made possible by the interaction of the different state variables constitute the *state space* (also known as *phase space*). Each point of a state space corresponds to a potential state of the system. As the system evolve from one state to another, the curve that emerges is known as the *trajectory* of the system. The set of all potential trajectories form the *phase portrait* of a dynamical system. That is, there will be states of the phase space that will not belong to the phase portrait for they will not be part of potential trajectories.

Some systems evolve in discrete steps. These are linear systems. Yet, cognition does not evolve that way. As van Gelder and Fort state in their seminal paper (1995, 2): “The heart of the problem is *time*. *Cognitive processes and their context unfold continuously and simultaneously in real time*. Computational models specify a discrete sequence of static internal states in arbitrary “step” time (t_1 , t_2 , etc.). Imposing the latter onto the former is like wearing shoes on your hands. You can do it, but gloves fit a whole lot better”. The ‘gloves’ for cognition are differential equations with non-linear terms. From a dynamic systems theory, the different processes that make up cognition can be seen as a non-linear dynamical system whose behavior is the trajectory through the phase space.

2 . *Glossary of dynamical system theory*

The definition of the following terms is not specific of enactive contexts, unless expressly indicated to the contrary, but a general definition consistent between different approaches to dynamic systems theory framework.

- Attractor: A curve that attracts at least some phase trajectories of the system that take place in the vicinity of said curve is called attractor of the dynamical system. The region of the system that surrounds the attractor is known as 'basin of attraction'. A system can have more than one attractor, and each attractor will have their own basins of attractions. In terms of cognitive activity, attractors correspond to favored states into which the system is inclined to fall and linger until a new input causes the transition to another state. In other words, an attractor is a preferred state at the lowest energy possible. According to van Gelder and Port (1995, 17): "particular actions are conceptualized as attractors in a space of possible bodily movements, and development of bodily skills is the emergence, and change in nature, of these attractors over time under the influence of factors such as bodily growth and the practice of the action itself". One notion related to attractor, is that of repellor or repeller. A repellor is the opposite of an attractor. It is a region of the phase space that separates different basins of attraction. In three dimensional representations of dynamic systems, the attractor is a region with negative elevation and a repellor a region with positive elevation.

- Affordance: According to classical definition offered by J. J. Gibson in an affordance is a possibility of action provided to the animal by the environment. That is, we perceive possibilities for action. We perceive the possibility of seating in a chair or drinking tap water with a glass. Yet, affordances are relational. They invite actions depending of numerous circumstances such as action capabilities of the agent, evolutionary aspects, cultural aspects, personal history (Withagen et al. 2012). One important aspect is that affordances are not just shaped by physical aspects, but also by social, and cultural ones. Another important feature of affordances is that they are interconnected. Affordances constitute 'field of affordances' –those affordances that are salient for a particular organism at a particular given time– or 'landscape of affordances' –the total of affordances available for a form of life in a given environment (Rietveld, E., Kiverstein, J. 2014).

- Constraint: According to Alicia Juarrero (2015, 514), a constraint is “any event, mechanism, or condition that alters a system’s probability space”. Classically, constraints are considered as conditions that limit the potential outcomes of a circumstance, but Juarrero’s definition opens the door to consider constraints not only as limiting circumstances, but also as enabling ones.

- Order parameter: a macrolevel pattern of organization that emerges out of the organization of individual parts of the system able to constrain the behavior of individual parts. According to Thompson (2010, 41), order parameter can be also regarded as collective variable, for it “describes a high-level or global characteristic of a system that emerges as a coherent and ordered pattern from the interaction of the system’s components”.

- Control parameter: a value of a parameter whose continuous qualitative change provokes qualitative change in the behavior of the system without being affected by the the system. One example of control parameter can be temperature. It changes the behavior of molecules in a system and, at a critical temperature, provokes critical

- Attunement: According to Shaun Gallagher (2020, 103), this attunement “is part of a mutual alignment that characterizes interactions and that can be specified in detail in their dynamic relations and the integration of the intrinsic temporalities of the agent’s movements”. This notion is related to that of resonance.

- Resonance: This is a popular term in ecological psychology. Vicente Raja has recently developed a thorough analysis of this notion as a basis of non-representational radical embodiment. According to Raja (2020, 5-6): “Resonance is a widely observed phenomenon in nature and has been described in several fields (e.g., acoustic resonance, mechanical resonance, orbital resonance, optical resonance, or electrical resonance). Put simply, resonance occurs when a vibrating system forces another system to vibrate at a greater amplitude at some specific frequencies -especially at those related to the latter’s natural frequency. A canonical example of resonance is the body of a violin or a guitar resonating to the vibration of one of its strings and amplifying its sound”.

- Metastability: Is a term from dynamic systems theory used in cognitive science to denote a regime of oscillatory activity in which the elements of the system exhibit tendencies to function autonomously at the same time as for coordinated activity (Fingelkurts and Fingelkurts 2004). In metastability energy is not necessary to go from one state to another. Metastability presents slower phases of integration of neural activity –dwells– and fast segregative moments –escapes– in which the global rhythm seems to reshuffle itself. The existence of traces of attractors instead of fixed attractors prevents the evolution from being absolutely stochastic. A monostable is a regime in which a system presents only one stable state. On the other hand, multistability is a regime in which a system presents two or more available collective states for the same value of the control parameter (Kelso, 1995). Yet, unlike in metastability, changes of state in multistability require energy to take place.

3 . Glossary of ENAMARE related concepts

Rhythm: The earliest preserved account of the word ῥυθμός (rhythμός) is found in a poem by Archilocus in which, according to Barletta (2020, 3), it denotes “a force that not only limits or constrains all humans [...] but one that also gives us form and meaning, pushing us always toward a mean between two forces”. This notion is related to the atomist idea of rhythμός as “the form in the instant that it is assumed by what is moving, mobile and fluid, the form of that which does not have organic consistency” (Benveniste 1971, 285-286). In particular, the –θμός form indicates not the final state of a process, but the way it presents itself to the human eye as it takes place (Benveniste 1971, 285). Rhythμός denotes the perceivable “pattern of a fluid element, or a letter arbitrarily shaped, of a robe which one arranges at one’s will, of a particular state or mood. It is the form as improvised, momentary, changeable” (Benveniste 1971, 286). In its earliest use, rhythμός meant a temporary interaction of forces. Nowadays the most widespread understanding of rhythm is as a regular temporal pattern of elements. We find iterations of this definition in dictionaries, papers, and scientific literature. The origins of this.

I have presented a definition of rhythm as “an evolving pattern of oscillations able to entrain other oscillations” (Vara Sanchez 2020). This conceptualization does not ignore the temporal aspect of rhythms – it is present in the word ‘evolving’ – but makes continuity and pervasiveness their main features. This extremely relational definition considers rhythms as particular patterns that emerge from the interaction of two or more oscillatory elements. Speaking of human beings, we can focus on the emergent rhythm of the contraction of the heart – caused by the interaction of electric impulses generated by cells of the sinoatrial node – but this rhythm can also be regarded as part of a bigger rhythm, along with other mechanical rhythms related to respiration and gastric activity that are reciprocally regulated. And the resultant bodily rhythm can be considered an element that makes part of a much more complex rhythm, together with brain and environmental oscillations, all of which enact nested dynamic constraints⁴ that affect the whole through entrainment and have an effect on experience. Yet, this does not mean that a unitary, constant oscillation along the body and the brain could be registered. It means that different oscillations are nested in such a way that variations in one of these local rhythms affect the whole rhythmicity. The different oscillations that we find in the body, brain, and environment not only serve their specific function, but

contribute to the enactment of an ongoing set of rhythmic constraints constitutive of cognition necessary for the modulation and attunement of the whole rhythm.

- Entrainment: Lakatos, Gross and Thut (2019, 890) define entrainment as “phase locking resulting from (predominantly) unidirectional coupling”. From their point of view, entrainment denotes the mechanisms by which periodic or almost periodic events from the environment – e.g., music, speech, movements, day-night cycles – drive the oscillatory activity in the perceiver’s brain, leading to the alignment – phase-locking in neuroscientific jargon – of their frequencies. I regard this to be a strong version of entrainment. However, there are weaker versions of it too. Many studies consider entrainment to mean not just perfect phase-locking, but also the general tendency toward this state (Pikovsky, Rosenblum, Kurths 2001). And their view it not as an exclusively unidirectional process, but as one involving two or more self-sustained oscillators. I believe that assuming these two conditions implies a weaker but more open version of entrainment, which is the one that I support in ENAMARE. That is, entrainment is a process between two or more oscillators in which there is a general tendency towards phase-locking. From my point of view, when Trost and Vuilleumier (2013) speak of perceptual, autonomic physiological, motor and social types of entrainment, they also back a weaker understanding of entrainment. And although the regulation between these different levels of entrainment is still open to discussion, Trost, Labbé, and Grandjean (2017, 105) suggest that these different types of entrainment are part of the same phenomenon.

4. Bibliography dynamic systems theory.

4.1 General dynamic systems theory bibliography

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